

Why CLEANDEM?

CLEANDEM seeks to introduce a technological breakthrough for dismantling and decommissioning (D&D) operations of nuclear sites, employing an Unmanned Ground Vehicle (UGV) Platform equipped with innovative radiological sensing probes.

CLEANDEM will deliver a unique platform that will support the end-users' operations — from the initial radiological assessment to the final characterization of the facility — while enabling their continuous monitoring during the D&D operations.

The CLEANDEM partners selected a specific set of technologies (sensors) already proven within the experience of this Consortium and with a maturity level between TRL5 and TRL7 (if considered to be applied for D&D specific applications). Such sensors only require a "specialization" through a short engineering phase for their implementation in the main selected D&D scenarios (actual experience in the field plus envisioned future scenarios).

TRL 4

TRL 5

Partial-scale prototype validation

TRL 6

Full-scale prototype field demonstration

TRL 7

Full-scale prototype in commercial conditions

TRL 8

Challenges addressed by CLEANDEM

- Improvement of D&D operations in terms of operators' exposure to radiation;
- time and cost;
- traceability.

- Demonstration that a single platform can successfully operate in all phases of D&D operations.
- Faster and more accurate data collection to ease and accelerate the clean-up process.

CLEANDEM partners

Impact

The overall impact and the innovation potential of CLEANDEM can be summarized in five keywords:

CLEANER

Reduce environmental impact by lowering environmental risks.

SAFER

Improve safety for workers and the population by minimizing human intervention.

FASTER

Reduce the duration of dismantling operations thanks to the autonomous operation of the robot acquiring measurements.

CHEAPER

Drastically reduce costs by minimizing time and cost associated to D&D operations through low-cost technologies and modular solutions.

BETTER

Improve the measurement quality by using multiple on-line probes in parallel and increase the reliability of measurement values and location.

Picture credit: Tecnalia

CLEANDEM

Cyber physical
Equipment for
unmanned Nuclear
DEcommissioning
Measurements

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The CLEANDEM methodology

PHASE 1

- Identification of technical specifications and state-of-the-art assessment of the technologies included in the CLEANDEM toolbox;
- Definition of several scenarios corresponding to the different phases of a D&D facility: initial radiological status, on-going operations, final characterization.

CLEANDEM results

1. SENSORS AND PLATFORM

CLEANDEM seeks to upgrade radiological sensors with:

- the improvement of **low-cost sensors for rapid neutron and gamma** (INFN's developments on the MiniRadMeter gamma counters/spectrometers and gamma-blind MiniSiLiF neutron counters) and **distributed dose rate mapping** (CEA-List's OSL optical fibers technology coupled to 3D shape-sensing to access narrow spaces);
- neutron/gamma detection and identification** sensors improvements (CAEN's PSD Phoswich alpha/beta large surface contamination monitor, CEA-List's upgrade of coded-aperture Nanopix gamma imager for hotspot localization);
- air and surface contamination monitoring** (ENEA's cryogenic system for radioactive radiocarbon dioxide monitoring $^{14}\text{CO}_2$, CEA-List's pixelated plastic scintillators for beta/gamma surface contamination).

Most of the sensors will be embedded on the RB-VOGUI **unmanned platform** equipped with a UR 5e robotic-arm upgraded by TECNALIA and ANSALDO for remote and autonomous operations.

2. DIGITAL TWIN

The CLEANDEM technologies will provide a 3D and fully detailed Digital Twin of the surveyed area augmented with radiological information provided by the sensors, thus enabling an efficient and effective planning of the dismantling actions and optimizing the nuclear waste sorting for reprocessing or for delivery to the final storage. The Digital Twin is able to give not only a clear and comprehensive view of the scenario under examination but

PHASE 2

- Development and optimization of the proposed technologies;
- Coupling between different technologies with the UGV platform and its localization and navigation technology;
- Transfer of all recorded data to the Digital Twin containing all up-to-date radiological information.

is also able to evolve with the decommissioning operations and provide a memory of the history of the site, becoming a valuable monitoring tool.

3. TRAINING, DEMONSTRATION AND MARKET ANALYSIS

Two work packages are dedicated to adapting the developments to the market and providing training and in-situ demonstrations through relevant use cases for end-users and stakeholders. SOGIN, with support from AiNT, developed a modular training program through a series of course units and set up an end-users network to investigate requirements.

A database of market indicators for cost analysis of the UGV platform for different business cases derived from the CONOPS use cases has been set by Orano.

FINAL PHASE

- Evaluation of the different technologies developed and upgraded;
- Coupling of a part of them with the UGV platform;
- Performance assessment of the full system in real D&D measurement conditions.

SENSORS ON PLATFORM

OTHER SENSORS

DIGITAL TWIN

TRAINING & DEMONSTRATION

